

ANALYSIS OF QUALIFIED PERSONNEL ISSUES IN CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In this article we do the analysis as well as identify cause of occurrence this problem. Finding methods problem solutions related to personnel employees in construction companies organizations.

Introduction

The issue of staff shortages in the construction industry acquires its validity in the 1990s, with construction came to a crisis in the relationship with a funding gap because of the immaturity of the concept of underdevelopment trading mechanism dwellings on the open market. The strategy of cooperatives or the distribution of housing through administrative bodies has led to a situation where the construction of housing in cities has almost completely ended. The Builder's profession is also unknown she didn't take advantage of the fame. Parents, concerned about the future welfare of their own children, were eager to provide them with the humanitarian training they needed at that time (legal, financial). Steel construction

qualifications are not required you need them enough. Business leaders can complain about this or that what's the big deal some of the skilled builders who worked in construction sites back in the Soviet period, pre-retirement or retirement age. At the same time, the problem of young workers remains very important. The training of modern graduates of construction faculties and institutes is also located at a low level, in the main priority in relation to the lack of motivation of students to study.

The 1st factor of the formed condition in this, then what are the graduates of construction institutes? They do not want to go to construction sites because of the unavailability of prestige of this type of work. 2-nd factor-the degree of wages fees that are not comparable to the degree of

liability. The 3rd factor is an almost absolute lack of practical skills after graduating from the University.

If you need to select one, then what's in Soviet the Union had a practical purpose. companies' patronage activities over educational institutions, which gave them a chance of success not only that it is only necessary to examine teaching AIDS, but also to compare the essence of training projects with the actual needs of production. In higher schools educational programs there are also production facilities practice, equal to as the norm, which turn out to be fruitless, so how the company's structure is not rather interested in wasting period and currency resources in training students, then what's wrong it does not give an impetus to the formation of a well-known professional stream.

Metod

One of the factors is the lack of normalized contacts between educational institutions and construction organizations. Because of this, the degree of training of young experts everywhere has the only significant disadvantage — a lack of about many actual abilities, according to the profession, but directly actual skills are also necessary for the employer.

Experts believe that what are the difficulties with personnel in the construction sector at the moment today's day are peculiar in no way not just with the goal of graduates of institutes, but also for graduates colleges and technical schools. The concept of training employees of mediocre level disappears: a specialist,

foremen, but so how are they doing — the most important companies in construction. So As with their skill, with their skill, with their industrial training. depending really in in this case, then what will be built. This public motivation that existed was formed after over the past years in the world, it has led to this, then what is everything without some people try to go to universities. moreover, it has become quite easy to get a certificate of the highest technical education. Also young generation of nothing does not want to linger on the degree of secondary special education.

Continuing education involves improvement professional within a lifetime, however, estimate it in context level education: initial professional vocational secondary, then higher professional supporting higher education.

The issue of employee training is also combined with this, then what young experts do society at an advanced age, certain with which none have encountered in practice with the technology of construction manufacturing also in no way do not seek to learn the latest used ones materials are also technological processes that often teach students according to outdated methods. In the '80s in previous years, the average age of the teacher was 35 years. At the present time, the average age of real teachers of municipal institutions is — 51.9. Average age of teachers with a scientific degree — 66 years old, «unshaded» students who have teaching experience of more than 20 years-64 years And the given, in its own order, thus no way does not provide the ability

to extract the required practical abilities that meet market conditions. This value can be marked as follows as the fifth root cause.

Results

Regardless of the that the professional problem of the construction sector is very critical, there are ways to solve it. Business, equal to as a carrier of the latest knowledge, it is more profitable to extract a ready-made professional, rather than risky to attach yourself to his training during the work period. Output could the wording be profitable for a public order with the purpose of educational institutions, but other than get support in passing through this is a great opportunity for students to continue their practical training and further employ promising graduates.

In If there is no employer role, this problem is not solved I can't find a solution to this problem. compliance with the with thus, the only method is this target orientation. If the organization sends a specific number of employees on University preparation, paying also exercising control the process of their teaching; and so way contains with them an agreement, according to which in the course of a particular stage of a period of qualified experts work assigned to them shall purchase employee labor the length of service, the probability of increasing labor qualifications, the work requirement and the probability of continuing working activities in this firm are also well-established the team. K By the word, given after all will be able to help me find it solving the issue of «turnover», what is it the same negative impact on the economy also

affects the formation of the sphere in General and the company in particular. During this period, only large firms are able to form target trends.

So In the same way, it is necessary to increase the control number of students' admission to construction professions; to make an integral increase in the qualification of employees within the framework of stereotypes of self-governing institutions of construction profile; to form a sector-wide research body.

There is an opinion that that one of the main difficulties can be directly forming similar training centers for construction firms. In this case, the training process will involve the company's experts, who have practical skills, an understanding of current needs and market trends.

During this period, a large the number of social institutions non-trading organizations also partnerships associated with the construction area involved a higher degree of prestige of the specialty of the Builder also of the interest of the young generation to follow in the profession to be in it. This is achieved by using the ad platform formation line, forums with the purpose of communication is young students from various corners of the country, training them in advanced technologies, due to specialist classes of key experts and organizations, as well as grant projects in the implementation of personal plans, as well as the formation of their own commercial.

Conclusion

It is possible to distribute the construction area in this way after all, through the school, the line of formation of specialized classes. Penza

has a similar practical program for example, at the moment 23 schools are preparing to conclude contracts on the formation of a construction profile in their own educational building. In-depth study of industrial lessons plus involvement of student teachers with the goal of special courses will be the

opportunity for teenagers to have the most accurate understanding of the specialty of the Builder, to consciously make their own selection in favor of this profile, also at admission to have basic knowledge that can help with further training.

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